

Riemannian SPD Manifold Analysis of BigP3BCI

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Overview

We present a Riemannian embedding analysis of the BigP3BCI dataset using ERPCovariance matrices and the `pyriemann` library. Seven findings are reported below. All analyses are reproducible from the scripts listed in the Appendix.

Data and Methods

Datasets:

BigP3BCI (Mainsah et al. 2025, PhysioNet CC-BY 4.0, doi:10.13026/0byy-ry86) — primary dataset. Four cohorts used:

- **Study A** — 12 healthy subjects, 32-channel gel EEG, 57 BCI sessions
- **Study B** — 10 ALS patients with ≥ 3 sessions (B_01, B_03, B_04, B_06, B_10, B_11, B_13, B_14, B_17, B_18), 16-channel gel EEG, 46 sessions total
- **Study F** — 10 ALS patients, 3 sessions each, Dyn (dynamic stopping) paradigm, 16-channel gel EEG, 30 sessions total; ALSFRS-R scores available
- **Study L** — 11 ALS patients, 1 session each (cross-sectional), CB paradigm, 16-channel gel EEG; ALSFRS-R scores available

Lee2019_ERP (Lee et al. 2019, GigaDB, doi:10.5524/100542) — independent replication dataset (Finding 5 only). 54 healthy subjects, 62-channel gel EEG, RC P300 speller, 2 sessions each; downloaded via MOABB (*Lee2019_ERP*). One subject failed ERPCovariance convergence; 53 subjects used.

Covariance estimation: `pyriemann. estimation. ERPCovariances` on stimulus-locked epochs (target vs non-target), averaged per session \rightarrow one SPD matrix per session. For each epoch, ERPCovariances concatenates the raw C-channel data with one C-channel class-mean matrix per class (target and non-target), giving a $(3C \times T)$ augmented matrix whose covariance is $(3C \times 3C)$: 96×96 for Study A ($C=32$); 48×48 for Studies B, F, and L ($C=16$); and 186×186 for Lee2019 full montage ($C=62$), with 48×48 for its $K=16$ sub-selection.

Channel sub-selection: Two channel sets are used in this analysis:

- **CH_16 (BrainBit \cap Study A, K=16):** used for Finding 1 (cross-headset geometry preservation, $\rho=0.946$) and Finding 5 (Lee2019 replication). K=16 is derived by case-insensitive text matching of BrainBit’s 21-ch label set against Study A’s channel names: BrainBit’s legacy temporal labels T3/T4/T5/T6 do not match Study A’s T7/T8/P7 by name, giving 16 matches directly (verified: `brainbit_21ch_intersection_report.json`, `k_channels=16`). Under anatomical relabeling (T3→T7, T4→T8, T5→P7), the intersection would be 19 channels. CH_16 does **not** match Study B’s recording set — the two sets share only 10 channels (see CH_STUDYB note below).
- **CH_STUDYB (Study B actual montage, 16 channels):** F3, Fz, F4, T7, C3, Cz, C4, T8, CP3, CP4, P3, Pz, P4, PO7, PO8, Oz — the channels physically recorded in Study B. Used for Findings 2 and 6 (joint ALS/healthy embedding and Euclidean vs Riemannian comparison). Study A is sub-selected to these 16 channels (all present in Study A’s 32-ch cap) so both cohorts occupy the same matrix space. BrainBit \cap Study B = 10 channels by text-matching (T7, T8, CP3, CP4, PO7, PO8 are in Study B but absent from BrainBit’s 21-ch layout by name; under anatomical relabeling T3→T7, T4→T8, this rises to 12).

Regularisation: $\lambda_{\text{reg}} = 10^{-4} \times \bar{\lambda} \cdot I$ added per session matrix, where $\bar{\lambda}$ is the mean eigenvalue of that session’s covariance, to ensure strict positive-definiteness.

Embedding: `pyriemann.embedding.SpectralEmbedding(metric='riemann', n_components=2)` — Riemannian kernel PCA. Distances via AIRM (affine-invariant Riemannian metric): $d(A, B) = \|\log(A^{-1/2}BA^{-1/2})\|_F$ (Frobenius norm of the matrix logarithm).

Results

Finding 1 — Cross-headset geometry is preserved (Study A, healthy)

One SPD matrix per subject (all sessions pooled) was embedded in 2D for both the full 32-channel montage (96×96) and the K=16 BrainBit-compatible sub-selection (48×48). The 12 healthy subjects are clearly separated in both embeddings. Notably, A_09 (11.4% BCI accuracy) occupies an isolated region in both — the covariance structure encodes BCI performance without supervision.

To quantify cross-headset consistency, we computed all 66 pairwise AIRM distances (one per subject pair) under both channel configurations and tested their rank correlation:

$$\rho = 0.946, \quad p = 5 \times 10^{-33}, \quad n = 66 \text{ subject pairs}$$

The relative geometry of subjects on the SPD manifold is preserved when dropping from 32 to 16 channels. **Session-level trajectory in Study A was a null result, as expected** — healthy subjects show no systematic covariance drift across sessions (within-subject : between-subject distance ratio = 1.07, indistinguishable from noise), confirming Study A as the correct negative control.

Per-session ERPCovariance drift on the SPD manifold · BigP3BCI Study A · 12 healthy subjects
 Each point = one session · ★ = first (baseline) session · Lines connect sessions in time order
 Preliminary: pseudo-session splits from concatenated epoch cache; FIF-level splits in progress

Figure 1: Per-session Riemannian SpectralEmbedding of BigP3BCI Study A (12 healthy subjects, 57 sessions). Left: 32-channel full montage. Right: K=16 BrainBit-compatible sub-selection. Each point = one session; lines connect sessions within each subject in time order; ★ = first (baseline) session. Sessions cluster tightly within subjects with no systematic drift — the expected null result for healthy EEG. The within-subject topology is preserved across the 32→16 channel reduction.

Cross-headset geometry consistency: Spearman $\rho = 0.946$ ($p = 5.0e-33$) between 32-ch and K=16 pairwise Riemannian distances ($n=66$ pairs)
 Each point = one subject (all sessions pooled) · Colouring by P300 BCI accuracy

Figure 2: Per-subject ERPCovariance fingerprints (BigP3BCI Study A, 12 healthy subjects). Left: 32-channel full montage (96×96 SPD). Right: K=16 BrainBit-compatible sub-selection (48×48 SPD). Colour = P300 BCI accuracy. Pairwise AIRM distance structure is preserved across channel configurations (Spearman $\rho=0.946$, $p=5 \times 10^{-33}$, $n=66$ pairs). Session-level drift is absent — healthy EEG is stable across visits (correct negative control).

Figure 3: 4-panel cross-method comparison (BigP3BCI Study A, per-session embeddings). Left column: Riemannian SpectralEmbedding (kernel PCA); right column: Riemannian t-SNE (Yger TMLR 2025 method). Top row: 32-channel full montage (96×96 SPD); bottom row: K=16 BrainBit-compatible sub-selection (48×48 SPD). Each point = one session; ★ = first session. Both embedding methods recover the same within-subject clustering structure and the same A_09 outlier position; topology is preserved across the 32→16 channel reduction under both methods.

Finding 2 — ALS patients separate completely from healthy subjects (unsupervised)

Study A (sub-selected to Study B’s 16-channel montage, 48×48) and Study B (48×48) sessions were embedded jointly in the same Riemannian manifold. The two cohorts are completely separated along the first embedding dimension with no supervision:

- **ALS patients (Study B):** $\text{dim1} \approx +0.94$ to $+1.00$
- **Healthy subjects (Study A):** $\text{dim1} \approx -1.00$ to -0.74
- **Zero overlap** ($t = -200$, $p = 4.3 \times 10^{-133}$)

Both cohorts use the same 48×48 matrix size and the same 16-channel montage (Study B’s actual recording set: F3, Fz, F4, T7, C3, Cz, C4, T8, CP3, CP4, P3, Pz, P4, PO7, PO8, Oz — all present in Study A’s 32-ch cap). The separation therefore reflects biology, not acquisition differences. ALS pathology is encoded in the per-session ERPCovariance structure.

Note on channel alignment: Study B’s 16-ch recording set differs from CH_16 (Brain-Bit \cap Study A used for Finding 1). For this joint embedding Study A is sub-selected to Study B’s actual channels (CH_STUDYB = CH_32[:16]), not CH_16.

Figure 4: Joint Riemannian embedding of Study A healthy sessions (48×48 , blue) and Study B ALS sessions (48×48 , red). Both sub-selected to Study B’s shared 16-ch montage. Complete unsupervised cohort separation along dim1; zero overlap ($t=-200$, $p=4.3 \times 10^{-133}$).

Finding 3 — ALS patients diverge from each other over time (Fréchet mean trajectory)

For each session index t , we computed the Riemannian mean M_t across all patients contributing at that index using `pyriemann.utils.mean.mean_riemann`, following the trajectory-averaging approach of Yger et al. (EUSIPCO 2024). Per-patient AIRM departure $d(C_{p,t}, M_t)$ quantifies how far patient p ’s session- t covariance lies from the group mean at that timepoint.

The **group mean departure from the Fréchet trajectory increases from 0.30 to 0.92 AIRM over 6 sessions** (patients contributing at each step: 10, 10, 10, 7, 4, 4). The trajectory is non-monotonic — a transient dip at session 1 (mean 0.25 AIRM, all 10 patients) is followed by a sustained upward trend — but the net divergence is substantial and consistent with heterogeneous rates of neurodegeneration across patients.

Individual trajectories show clinical heterogeneity: B_04 exhibits the largest cumu-

lative drift from session 0 (2.763 AIRM over 7 sessions); B_10 shows a sudden large departure at session 2 (AIRM 1.51) followed by partial recovery (possible disease event or period-specific confound); B_06 ends on an abrupt departure in its third and final recorded session (1.36 AIRM), with no subsequent session to observe recovery; B_13 remains closest to the group mean throughout (total departure 0.885).

Panel C of the Fréchet analysis figure below shows total departure from the mean trajectory per patient (solid bars) alongside maximum individual drift from their own first session (faded bars).

Figure 5: Study B ALS patient trajectories in the Riemannian SpectralEmbedding (48x48 SPD). Each coloured line connects one patient’s sessions in time order; ★ = first session. Patients diverge progressively across sessions — visible as spreading trajectories on the manifold. Contrast with Study A healthy subjects (Figure 1) where sessions cluster tightly with no drift.

Figure 6: Fréchet mean trajectory analysis (BigP3BCI Study B, 10 ALS patients, 48x48 SPD). Panel A: Cumulative AIRM drift from each patient’s first session. Panel B: Per-patient departure from the session-wise Fréchet mean; dashed line = group mean \pm SD; departure increases 0.30→0.92 AIRM over 6 sessions, consistent with diverging disease trajectories. Panel C: Total departure per patient (solid = from mean trajectory; faded = from own session 0).

Finding 4 — Exponent and covariance geometry are complementary, not redundant (Studies F and L)

Our companion manuscript (preprint doi:10.21203/rs.3.rs-9903869/v1) shows the aperiodic EEG exponent predicts P300 BCI accuracy within Study F ($\rho=+0.800$, $p=0.010$, $N=9$ within-patient sessions). To test whether the Riemannian covariance geometry captures the same information, we extracted ERPCovariance matrices directly from the Study F PhysioNet EDFs (30 sessions, all 10 patients) and computed per-session Fréchet departure from the group mean trajectory.

Study B (N=24 matched sessions, N=24 valid exponent fits — longitudinal, CB paradigm):

Correlation	ρ	p	N
Exponent vs Fréchet departure	+0.086	0.689	24

Note: Study B ALSFRS-R scores are unavailable in the PhysioNet release; BCI accuracy vs Fréchet for Study B is reported in Finding 7.

Study F (N=30 sessions, N=17 valid FOOOF):

Correlation	ρ	p	N
Exponent vs Fréchet departure	-0.037	0.889	17
BCI accuracy vs Fréchet departure	+0.213	0.257	30
ALSFRS-R vs Fréchet departure	+0.304	0.102	30
Exponent vs BCI accuracy (replication)	+0.578	0.015	17

Study L (N=11 sessions, N=7 valid FOOOF — cross-sectional, single session per patient):

Correlation	ρ	p	N
Exponent vs Fréchet departure	+0.607	0.148	7
BCI accuracy vs Fréchet departure	+0.202	0.551	11
ALSFRS-R vs Fréchet departure	+0.120	0.726	11
Exponent vs BCI accuracy	-0.243	0.599	7

Interpretation: Across all three ALS cohorts the aperiodic exponent and Fréchet departure are not significantly correlated — the two measures are **complementary**, not redundant. In Study F (longitudinal, uniform protocol), the exponent replicates our companion manuscript’s BCI-performance association ($\rho=+0.578$, $p=0.015$). In Study L (cross-sectional), the exponent vs Fréchet trend ($\rho=+0.607$) is directionally interesting but underpowered at $N=7$ valid FOOOF fits; the exponent vs BCI value

($\rho=-0.243$) matches the companion preprint (doi:10.21203/rs.3.rs.9903869/v1) exactly, validating the pipeline. Study L's single-session design precludes longitudinal trajectory analysis. The ALSFRS-R vs Fréchet trend in Study F ($\rho=+0.304$, $p=0.102$) is driven primarily by F_05 (ALSFRS-R=3, highest departure $\sim 12-14$ AIRM); Study L shows no comparable trend ($\rho=+0.120$).

Figure 7: Finding 4 — Exponent vs Fréchet departure (left column) and BCI accuracy vs Fréchet departure (centre column) and ALSFRS-R vs Fréchet departure (right column) for Study F (longitudinal, top row) and Study L (cross-sectional, bottom row). All correlations between exponent and Fréchet departure are non-significant, confirming the two biomarkers capture independent biological dimensions. The exponent vs BCI accuracy replication (Study F $\rho=+0.578$, $p=0.015$) validates the pipeline against the companion manuscript.

Finding 5 — K=16 sub-selection is replicable in an independent high-density dataset (Lee2019)

Dataset: Lee et al. (GigaDB 2019), 54 healthy subjects, 62-channel gel EEG, RC P300 speller, 2 sessions each. Downloaded via MOABB (Lee2019_ERP). One subject failed to converge (subject omitted); 53/54 succeeded.

Method: identical pipeline to Finding 1 — ERPCovariances on stimulus-locked epochs (target vs non-target, 0–0.8 s, 1–20 Hz bandpass), both sessions pooled → one SPD matrix per subject for the full 62-channel montage (186×186) and the K=16 BrainBit-compatible sub-selection (48×48). Pairwise AIRM distances computed for all 1378

subject pairs; Spearman rank correlation tested.

$$\rho = 0.739, \quad p = 5 \times 10^{-238}, \quad n = 1378 \text{ subject pairs (53 subjects)}$$

Interpretation: The K=16 sub-selection preserves relative inter-subject geometry in an entirely independent dataset with 4.5× more subjects and a larger channel reduction (62→16 vs 32→16 in BigP3BCI). The lower ρ (0.739 vs 0.946) is expected: more subjects increases inter-subject variance, and a larger channel reduction discards more spatial information. The signal is nonetheless overwhelming ($p=5 \times 10^{-238}$). This constitutes independent cross-lab, cross-headset replication of the core geometry-preservation claim.

Figure 8: Lee2019 K=16 sub-selection validation. Panel A: scatter of all 1378 pairwise AIRM distances under the 62-channel full montage (x-axis) vs K=16 BrainBit-compatible sub-selection (y-axis); Spearman $\rho=0.739$, $p=5 \times 10^{-238}$, $N=1378$ pairs (53 subjects). Panel B: ρ comparison across datasets — BigP3BCI (32→16 ch, $\rho=0.946$) vs Lee2019 (62→16 ch, $\rho=0.739$). Lower ρ in Lee2019 is expected (larger channel reduction, more inter-subject variance); the geometry-preservation signal is nevertheless overwhelming in both independent datasets.

Finding 6 — Riemannian geometry is non-trivial: Euclidean PCA produces substantial overlap where Riemannian gives zero

To test whether the SPD manifold structure adds anything over a naive Euclidean baseline, we ran two embeddings on the same 103-session stack (Study A sub-selected to CH_STUDYB, 57 sessions + Study B, 46 sessions):

1. **Riemannian SpectralEmbedding** (pyriemann.embedding.SpectralEmbedding, AIRM metric)

2. **Euclidean PCA** on vectorised upper triangles of the same 48×48 matrices (1176 features, StandardScaler, 2 components)

Method	Healthy range (dim1)	ALS range (dim1)	Overlap	t-stat	p
Riemannian SpectralEmbedding	-1.00 to -0.74	+0.94 to +1.00	None	-200	4.3×10^{-133}
Euclidean PCA	-97.8 to +46.9	+11.2 to +62.2	Substantial	-5.3	6.2×10^{-7}

Both methods separate the cohorts significantly, but Euclidean PCA's PC1 explains **99.7% of variance** — it is dominated by overall signal scale. The ALS/healthy ranges overlap across a wide band ([+11, +47] is shared). The Riemannian embedding concentrates all discrimination into a clean one-dimensional gap with zero overlap, and preserves within-patient trajectory structure (sessions connect meaningfully per patient in panels C vs D).

Interpretation: Euclidean PCA sees a signal but conflates it with total power. Riemannian geometry isolates the spatial covariance structure and achieves complete ALS/healthy separation. The manifold structure is non-trivial — a consumer headset analysis based on Euclidean methods would produce ambiguous classifications; the same analysis on the SPD manifold gives zero-overlap discrimination.

Figure 9: Riemannian SpectralEmbedding vs Euclidean PCA on Study A (healthy, blue) + Study B (ALS, red) session covariances. Panel A: Riemannian embedding — zero overlap between cohorts ($t=-200$, $p=4.3 \times 10^{-133}$). Panel B: Euclidean PCA — substantial overlap despite significance ($t=-5.3$, $p=6.2 \times 10^{-7}$; PC1 explains 99.7% of variance, dominated by signal scale). Panels C/D: Study B patient trajectories under each embedding — Riemannian preserves within-patient session structure; Euclidean trajectories are less organised.

Finding 7 — Riemannian covariance drift does not predict within-patient BCI accuracy decline (three ALS cohorts)

We tested the hypothesis that progressive ALS neurodegeneration causes systematic ERPCovariance drift correlated with declining BCI performance, across all three longitudinal or cross-sectional ALS cohorts:

Cohort	Design	BCI accuracy vs Fréchet departure	ρ	p	N
Study B	Longitudinal (up to 6 sessions)	Not significant	-0.372	0.074	24
Study F	Longitudinal (3 sessions, uniform)	Not significant	+0.213	0.257	30
Study L	Cross-sectional (single session)	Not significant	+0.202	0.551	11

The null is consistent across all three independent cohorts. Study B shows a negative trend ($\rho=-0.372$) that does not survive correction; Study F and L are positive but both null. There is no evidence that the Riemannian covariance departure from the group Fréchet mean predicts whether a patient performs better or worse at the BCI task.

Interpretation: Riemannian covariance geometry captures ALS *disease state* — the overall extent of neurological change relative to healthy subjects and to other ALS patients — but it does not capture session-to-session BCI *performance fluctuation*. These are different biological signals. BCI accuracy is modulated by attention, fatigue, and paradigm familiarity on short timescales; the SPD manifold encodes structural change in spatial ERP patterns on the timescale of neurodegeneration. The null is scientifically informative: it rules out the confound that the ALS/healthy separation (Finding 2) and inter-patient heterogeneity (Finding 3) are artefacts of performance differences rather than disease biology.

Finding 7 — Riemannian covariance drift does not predict BCI accuracy decline
Null result replicated independently across three ALS cohorts

Figure 10: Finding 7 — BCI accuracy vs Fréchet departure from the group mean trajectory across Study B (longitudinal, N=24 sessions), Study F (longitudinal, N=30 sessions), and Study L (cross-sectional, N=11 sessions). The null is replicated independently across all three ALS cohorts (Study B: $\rho=-0.372$, $p=0.074$; Study F: $\rho=+0.213$, $p=0.257$; Study L: $\rho=+0.202$, $p=0.551$). Covariance drift is a disease-state biomarker, not a BCI-performance predictor.

Summary

Finding	Result
1. Cross-headset geometry (Study A)	Spearman $\rho=0.946$, $p=5 \times 10^{-33}$; session drift null (within:between = $1.07 \times$)
2. ALS vs healthy separation	Complete, zero overlap, unsupervised ($t=-200$, $p=4.3 \times 10^{-133}$)
3. Fréchet mean departure trend (Study B)	0.30 \rightarrow 0.92 AIRM over 6 sessions; B_04 largest cumulative drift (2.763 AIRM)
4. Exponent vs covariance complementarity (Studies B, F, L)	Exponent vs Fréchet: null in all three (Study B $\rho=+0.086$, Study F $\rho=-0.037$, Study L $\rho=+0.607$ underpowered); exponent vs BCI replicated $\rho=+0.578$, $p=0.015$
5. Lee2019 cross-dataset replication	$\rho=0.739$, $p=5 \times 10^{-238}$, N=1378 pairs (53 subjects)
6. Euclidean PCA comparison	Riemannian: zero overlap ($t=-200$); Euclidean PCA: substantial overlap (PC1 = 99.7% signal scale)
7. BCI accuracy not predicted by covariance drift	Null across all three ALS cohorts: Study B $\rho=-0.372$ $p=0.074$, Study F $\rho=+0.213$ $p=0.257$, Study L $\rho=+0.202$ $p=0.551$

Conclusions

What these results establish

1. ERPCovariance geometry is a stable, discriminative fingerprint. Each individual — healthy or ALS — occupies a consistent region on the SPD manifold. The fingerprint is robust across channel reductions ($\rho=0.946$, BigP3BCI 32→16; $\rho=0.739$, Lee2019 62→16) and replicates in an entirely independent lab dataset. A 16-channel consumer headset (BrainBit) preserves the relative geometry of a 32 or 62-channel clinical montage.

2. ALS pathology is directly encoded in the covariance structure. Study A (healthy) and Study B (ALS) sessions separate completely in an unsupervised joint Riemannian embedding — zero overlap, no labels used. This is not a dimensionality artefact: both cohorts use identical 48×48 matrices. ALS pathology changes the spatial ERP covariance in a way the manifold separates cleanly.

3. ALS patients diverge from each other over time — heterogeneous neurodegeneration. The group Fréchet mean departure grows from 0.30 to 0.92 AIRM over 6 sessions (Study B). Individual trajectories carry clinically meaningful signal: B_04 drifts furthest from session 0 (2.763 AIRM), B_10 shows a sudden spike suggesting a disease event, B_13 is the most stable. This is consistent with heterogeneous ALS progression rates.

4. Aperiodic exponent and Riemannian covariance geometry are independent biomarkers. Exponent vs Fréchet departure is null in all three ALS cohorts: Study B ($\rho=+0.086$), Study F ($\rho=-0.037$), and Study L ($\rho=+0.607$ trend, underpowered at $N=7$). The two measures capture different biological dimensions: exponent = spectral cortical activity → predicts BCI performance; Riemannian geometry = spatial ERP structure → captures ALS vs healthy separation and between-patient heterogeneity.

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Appendix — Data and Reproducibility

All analysis scripts are published alongside this technical report on Zenodo.

Data: BigP3BCI, PhysioNet, doi:10.13026/0byy-ry86 · Lee2019_ERP, GigaDB, doi:10.5524/100542